

Wachendorfia brachyandra

Short-stamen butterfly-lily

© N Illing

Group: Monocot

Size: 20 – 65 cm.

Distribution:

W. brachyandra is endemic to the Cape floral region.

Importance:

Wachendorfia brachyandra is one of only five known species worldwide that exhibits floral asymmetry in the form of enantiostyly. Studying this species will help improve understanding of pollination adaptations in fynbos plants.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 90.7 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 9.71 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 0.36 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.3% [Single: 80.2%, Duplicated: 19.1%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 711.38 kilobases

Contig number: 4 419

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Date Published: 2026-03-09

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18922745>

